

INTEGRATING PHRASEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE INTO THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE CURRICULUM

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Abstract. *This thesis is about the integration of phraseological competence into language curricula that is crucial for enhancing learners’ communicative proficiency. This involves designing curricula that prioritize phraseology, employing instructional strategies like explicit instruction and input enhancement, and selecting appropriate materials. Such integration facilitates learners’ acquisition of multi-word units for effective communication.*

Keywords: *phraseological competence, language curriculum, instructional strategies, material selection, formulaic expressions, communicative proficiency, corpus-based tools, multi-word units, communicative interactions*

Integrating phraseological competence into the curriculum is an essential aspect of language education, aiming to enhance learners’ ability to use multi-word units effectively in communication. This integration involves the development of curriculum designs that prioritize the teaching and learning of phraseology, as well as the implementation of instructional strategies and the selection of appropriate materials and resources to support learners’ acquisition of phraseological competence.

Boers, Demecheleer, Coxhead, and Webb emphasize the importance of incorporating explicit instruction on phraseological patterns into language curricula [1]. They argue that learners benefit from focused instruction that helps them recognize and understand collocations, idioms, and formulaic expressions in context. By providing learners with explicit explanations and examples of phraseological patterns, educators can facilitate the acquisition and internalization of these multi-word units.

Furthermore, input enhancement techniques, as suggested by Ellis, Simpson-Vlach, and Maynard, can be valuable in integrating phraseological competence into the curriculum [2]. Input enhancement involves highlighting and enhancing learners’ exposure to phraseological expressions in authentic language input, such as texts, audiovisual materials, and communicative interactions. By drawing learners’ attention to phraseological patterns in context, educators can help them develop a better understanding of how these expressions are used in real-world communication.

In addition to instructional strategies, the selection of suitable materials and resources is crucial for integrating phraseological competence into the curriculum. Nattinger and DeCarrico stress the importance of using corpus-based resources to identify and study phraseological patterns in authentic language data [3]. Corpus-based tools and resources provide educators with access to large collections of language samples, allowing them to explore the frequency, collocational patterns, and pragmatic features of multi-word units in various contexts.

Moreover, authentic texts and materials play a vital role in supporting learners’ acquisition of phraseological competence. Pawley and Syder emphasize the significance of exposing learners to authentic language use, including idiomatic expressions and formulaic sequences, in order to develop their communicative skills [4]. Authentic texts provide learners with opportunities to

encounter phraseological expressions in context, allowing them to develop a deeper understanding of how these expressions are used in real-world communication.

Also, integrating phraseological competence into the curriculum is essential to address the gap between traditional language teaching methods and the communicative demands of real-world language use. It helps learners develop a deeper understanding of the cultural and pragmatic aspects of language use.

In conclusion, integrating phraseological competence into the curriculum requires careful consideration of curriculum design, instructional strategies, and the selection of appropriate materials and resources. By incorporating explicit instruction, input enhancement techniques, and authentic materials, educators can effectively support learners' acquisition of phraseological competence and enhance their communicative proficiency.

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